

Measurement of Solar Noise Temperature in Ku-Band using a Satellite Broadcast Receiver

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Abstract—Twice per year, every geostationary communication satellite is seen from the Earth with the Sun transiting behind it, causing the receivers whose beams are directed towards this satellite to pick up an interfering noise due to the solar microwave radiation. The assessment of this additional noise is of great importance not only in satellite broadcasting, but also in nowcasting and climate change monitoring applications, when opportunistic rainfall measurement based on satellite downlinks is employed. As matter of fact, the latter case requires accurate real-time measurement of the received signal level and prompt management of non-rain related alterations. This paper illustrates an experimental campaign, carried out during a solar transit behind a Ku-band broadcasting satellite, and provides a numerical evaluation of the Sun noise temperature.

I. INTRODUCTION

Let consider the microwave (μW) downlink from a geostationary satellite (GEOS) to an Earth station (ES), for direct-to-home (DTH) TV broadcasting in C-, or Ku-, or Ka-band. Twice per year, the ES sees the apparent path of the Sun across the sky to pass behind the satellite [1]. This is termed “Sun transit” and, in the Northern Hemisphere, happens a few days before the March equinox and a few days after the October equinox. During the transits, the Sun causes strong interference in the the μW bands on the ES receiver, which sums up to the background noise (cosmic, atmospheric, ground and receiver electronics contributions). The detrimental effects of Sun transits range from partial degradation, i.e., signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) reduction, to outage, i.e., the total destruction of the useful signal, and this is why this phenomenon is also known as “Sun fade” or “Sun outage”. The quantitative assessment of the noise increase due Sun transits in GEOS-based systems is of great practical importance: i) for downlink design in satellite broadcasting [2]; ii) for opportunistic rainfall estimate based on attenuation measurement in GEOS downlinks [3], in nowcasting services and climate change monitoring (e.g., the H2020 SCORE project, <https://score-eu-project.eu>). In particular, the latter case requires accurate real-time measurements of the received signal level and prompt management of non-rain related SNR alterations which may cause false detection of rain events. In this paper we will experimentally investigate the transit of the Sun behind a Ku-band broadcasting GEOS, and we assess the amount of μW noise increase experienced by a DTH receiver.

II. MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

The measurement system used in this case study consists of a commercial-grade integrated DTH satellite receiver called

Fig. 1. The IoT FIRST terminal and the offset satellite dish (left). Location of the terminal NEFOCAST-ITA-PI-002X (43.6962°N, 10.4277°E) (right).

Fig. 2. Sun transit behind a GEOS.

IoT FIRST terminal (www.egatel.es) and marketed by Eutelsat (www.eutelsat.com). Thanks to its optimized form-factor, this receiving device can be mounted in the focus of a conventional offset dish (Fig. 1 left). The ES used for the measurements is located in Pisa, Italy (43.6962°N, 10.4277°E). (Fig. 1, right), and belongs a sensor network deployed for experimental purposes across Central Italy during the Nefocast project [4] and the ID of the ES is NEFOCAST-ITA-PI-002X. The IoT FIRST Terminal is an innovative low-cost and small-size device, supporting both interactive TV services, and Internet of things (IoT) and machine-to-machine (M2M) applications, thanks to its two-way capability: i) forward link (FL) in the 10-13 GHz Ku-band with DVB-S2 (digital video broadcasting via satellite 2nd generation) receiver; ii) return link (RL) in the 14 GHz Ku-band with low-power ground-to-satellite transmitter carrying the receiver status, including the FL SNR, plus IoT sensor data. The RL enables thus the receiver to send its FL SNR measurements via the EUROBIS IoT FIRST satellite platform and Eutelsat 10A satellite in 10°E orbital position, to a remote data collection and processing center. The measurements presented in this work have been

made on the FL signal with frequency $f_c = 11.345$ GHz, vertical polarization, QPSK (quadrature-phase shift keying) modulation and coding rate 4/5 [4]. The ES receiving antenna is a conventional offset dish with diameter $D = 0.8$ m for satellite TV reception. Assuming an efficiency 0.7, we get the gain along the boresight $G_R = 38$ dBi and the -3dB angular beamwidth $\theta_{3\text{dB}} = 2.32^\circ$ (see [2], Sect. 5.2).

III. SATELLITE SIGNAL DATASET

Twice a year, around equinoxes [1], Sun transits cause deep notches on the SNR measured at the satellite receiver. For a 80 cm-diameter dish, every notch has a duration of approximately 20 minute and occurs every day over a period of a dozen of days. We used a dataset containing SNR readings, taken every minute from Feb. 26 to Mar. 7, 2022, by NEFOCAST-ITA-PI-002X station from the satellite Eutelsat 10A at 10°E . The SNR readings are in the form of the ratio $\eta = E_s/N_0$, wherein E_s is the average RF received energy during one QPSK symbol interval and N_0 is the one-sided noise power spectral density (PSD) [4]. The dataset in Fig. 3 exhibits a series of deep notches caused by Sun transits, occurring daily around 11:30 UTC. The ES and the satellite have almost the same longitude, and hence the transits occur around local noon (the standard time of ES location is UTC+1).

Fig. 3. Record of SNR from satellite Eutelsat 10A, measured in Pisa, 2022.

IV. SOLAR NOISE TEMPERATURE DERIVATION

We denote with: i) $t_n = n\tau$ the n th sampling instant of the receiver, where τ is the sampling interval (30 seconds); ii) $t_0 = n_0\tau$ and $t_1 = n_1\tau$ the start and the end instants of the notch, respectively; iii) $E_s(n\tau)$ the received energy per symbol (time-varying, due to residual orbit inclination); iv) $N_0^{(b)}$ the PSD of the background noise only (assumed constant during the transit, about 20 minutes), given by [4]

$$N_0^{(b)} = k \left[\frac{T_C}{L} + T_M \left(\frac{L-1}{L} \right) + T_G + T_R \right], \quad (1)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant, L is the atmospheric attenuation, T_C , T_M , T_G , T_R are the noise temperatures of cosmos, meteorological formations, ground and receiver hardware, respectively (numerical values in [4]); v) $N_0^{(S)}(n\tau)$ the time-varying overall noise PSD during the Sun transit

$$N_0^{(S)}(n\tau) = k \left[\frac{T_X(n\tau)}{L} + T_M \left(\frac{L-1}{L} \right) + T_G + T_R \right] \quad (2)$$

where $T_X(n\tau) = T_C + T_S(n\tau)$ includes the contributions of extraterrestrial sources (cosmos and the Sun); vi) $\eta(n\tau) = E_s(n\tau)/N_0^{(S)}(n\tau)$ the samples of the SNR during the Sun transit; vii) $\eta(n\tau)^{(\text{ref})} = E_s(n\tau)/N_0^{(b)}$ the reference SNR level, which is calculated by linear interpolation between the sample at the start of the transit $\eta(t_0)$ and the one at the end $\eta(t_1)$. From vi) and vii), we get for the n th sample during the sun transit

$$E_s(n\tau) = \eta(n\tau) \cdot N_0^{(S)}(n\tau) = \eta(n\tau)^{(\text{ref})} \cdot N_0^{(b)} \quad (3)$$

Replacing (1) – (2) in (3), and solving for $T_S(n\tau)$ we obtain the sun noise temperature values depicted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Sun noise temperature derived from SNR measurements by the IoT First terminal in Pisa during the sun transits close the March equinox in 2022.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Sun noise temperature in Ku-band was measured during the transit in Spring 2022, with a dish for satellite TV. Further work is needed to validate the results and to assess their sensitivity w.r.t. solar activity and the 11-year sunspot cycle.

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